

DEVELOPMENT OF AGRICULTURAL INSECTS THROUGH EXPERIMENTAL LIGHTTRAPS TO IMPROVE ELECTROPHYSICAL CONTROL METHODS

Sapaev Bayramdurdi

Tashkent State Agrarian University

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Annotatsiya: Light traps emitting various spectra are considered for monitoring and determining the development phases of agricultural insect pests, created on the basis of the latest scientific achievements using semiconductor materials operating in stand-alone operation. The devices are assembled from semiconductor leds, twilight relays and rechargeable batteries used as a power source, and silicon solar cells, considered a typical representative of semiconductor materials necessary for recharging batteries. The main goal of this work is to determine the phases of the active development of agricultural pests and, on the basis of this, create systems of environmentally friendly methods: biological and electrophysical for pest control.

Key words: of agricultural pests and, on the basis of this, create systems, leds, twilight relays and rechargeable, source, and silicon solar cells, considered, pest control methods; light traps, solar panels, twilight relays.

Introduction

Insects living in the surrounding biosphere have a significant impact on human life and the fruits of his labor, both positive (pollination of flowering plants, destruction of insect pests) and negative (destruction of crops, harvested crops, etc.). In this regard, insects are divided into beneficial insects and insect pests [2]. It is necessary to analyze existing methods of combating agricultural pests, improve and develop new methods based on the analysis, and based on the results of the conducted research, find optimal combinations of methods of combating agricultural pests. Increasing the yield of agricultural crops is the most important problem of agricultural production, directly related to ensuring the country's food security. Currently, agricultural production losses account for up to 40% of the crop as a result of the actions of weeds, pests, and diseases. Therefore, successful crop production is impossible without a comprehensive crop protection system against agricultural pests and diseases. There are four main methods: agrotechnical, biological, mechanical and chemical. At various stages of the development of agricultural production, the importance of methods in the general protection system has changed significantly [7]. Acceptable crop preservation is provided by the methods of protecting gardens from pests given in [4]. Favorable conditions for the development and growth, increasing the

resistance of plants to disease and pest damage during timely agrotechnical measures are shown. The disadvantages of existing methods in terms of their environmental friendliness and labor intensity are highlighted in [7]. The work [1] is devoted to the topical issue of protecting berry crops from insect pests with environmentally safe biological preparations. In the recent period in agricultural production, more and more attention is paid to the introduction of electrical technologies with an appropriate set of equipment [11, 13-15, 8-10]. Electrical technologies make it possible to make a sharp transfer of agricultural production to a new level with higher qualitative and quantitative indicators, with minimal economic costs [15, 11]. Many insects, especially nocturnal ones, demonstrate positive phototaxis under artificial lighting. In [13], traps are used to monitor and manage insect pest populations and play a crucial role in the physical control of pests. The effective use of light traps to attract insect pests is an important topic in the application of integrated pest control. The phototactic reactions of insects vary depending on the species, the characteristics of light and the physiological status of insects. In addition, light can cause several biological reactions, including biochemical, physiological, molecular and physical changes in insects [14].

The minimal availability of rice on the market is caused by a shortage of rice stock in warehouses due to the presence of warehouse pests. In addition to reducing the quantity and quality of rice, they significantly increase the financial losses of farmers. In [8], a complete trap method is proposed – a combination of physical and chemical control. The control was carried out by purple lights and chemical pesticides, humidifiers with multicolored lights and insect pheromones. The results showed that the population of warehouse pests is significantly reduced, and the quality of rice increases. Thus, in modern agricultural production, there is an acute problem of the transition of control from a chemical method that pollutes the environment to biological and physical, environmentally friendly methods of pest control. Based on the above, specialists and scientists of the agricultural sector need to find optimal ways and methods of combating agricultural pests, only in this case it is possible to increase the yields of farmland.

Materials and methods.

The research was based on electrophysical methods, which, in our opinion, are the most effective and environmentally friendly. In addition, an integrated plant protection method was used, combining biological and electrophysical methods for monitoring and killing insects and butterflies. Results and discussion. In

recent years, research institutions have developed and are introducing into production complex systems of crop protection from pests, diseases and weeds, which provide for rational use and a combination of organizational, economic, agrotechnical and other measures. The main task of plant protection from insect pests and diseases is the complete elimination or reduction of crop losses to economically imperceptible sizes based on the use of integrated plant protection systems that are safe for humans and the environment. Scientists have done a lot of work to establish the species composition of pests, identify diseases, determine harmfulness, develop measures to combat the most dangerous pests and plant diseases. Integrated plant protection is the most promising way to solve the problem. A set of rational techniques used on the basis of information about the species, population size and ratios of harmful and beneficial insects in the array of agricultural land, the phase of development, the timing of insect harmfulness, etc. The quality of monitoring the number and type of insect pests is determined by conducting integrated plant protection, which includes chemical and electrophysical methods. Let's take a closer look at the methods of electrophysical pest control, which include electric light traps. Modern promising methods of accounting for flying insects with positive phototaxis (the property of cells and microorganisms to orient themselves and move towards or away from a light source, characteristic primarily of phototrophic – the common name of organisms that use light as an energy source) should include light traps. They allow with little time and money to obtain objective information about the species and sexual composition, the timing and dynamics of flight, the maturation of egg products and the fertility of many types of agricultural pests.

Conclusion

Thus, the created installations, which represent an improved integrated method, are environmentally safe, easy to use and do not require frequent interventions. In the near future, it is necessary to improve devices based on photovoltaic converters (FEP) and LEDs emitting waves of various lengths, as well as twilight relays, and monitor the number and phases of insect pest development: which spectra attract more beneficial or harmful insects. After the experiments carried out, it is necessary to determine the optimal options for catching harmful insects, to start mass production of light traps for timely provision of agricultural enterprises.

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